

VALIDATION OF INERTIAL AND OPTICAL NAVIGATION TECHNIQUES FOR SPACE APPLICATIONS WITH UAVS

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ABSTRACT

PERIGEO is an R&D project, funded by the INNPRONTA 2011-2014 programme from Spanish CDTI, which aims to investigate the use of UAV technologies and processes for the validation of space oriented technologies. For this purpose, among different space missions and technologies, a set of activities for absolute and relative navigation are being carried out to deal with the attitude and position estimation problem from a temporal image sequence from a camera on the visible spectrum and/or Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) sensor. The process is covered entirely: from sensor measurements and data acquisition (images, LiDAR ranges and angles), data pre-processing (calibration and co-registration of camera and LIDAR data), features and landmarks extraction from the images and image/LiDAR-based state estimation.

In addition to image processing area, classical navigation system based on inertial sensors is also included in the research. The reason of combining both approaches is to enable the possibility to keep navigation capability in environments or missions where the radio beacon or reference signal as the GNSS satellite is not available (as for example an atmospheric flight in Titan). The rationale behind the combination of those systems is that they complement each other. The INS is capable of providing accurate position, velocity and full attitude estimations at high data rates. However, they need an absolute reference observation to compensate the time accumulative errors caused by inertial sensor inaccuracies. On the other hand, imaging observables can provide absolute and relative positioning and attitude estimations. However they need that the sensor head is pointing toward ground (something that may not be possible if the carrying platform is maneuvering) to provide accurate estimations and they are not capable of provide some hundreds of Hz that can deliver an INS. This mutual complementarity has been observed in PERIGEO and because of this they are combined into one system.

The inertial navigation system implemented in PERIGEO is based on a classical loosely coupled INS/GNSS approach that is very similar to the implementation of the INS/Imaging navigation system that is mentioned above.

The activities envisaged in PERIGEO cover the algorithms development and validation and technology testing on UAVs under representative conditions. Past activities have covered the design and development of the algorithms and systems. This paper presents the most recent activities and results on the area of image processing for robust estimation within PERIGEO, which are related with the hardware platforms definition (including sensors) and its integration in UAVs. Results for the tests performed during the flight campaigns in representative outdoor environments will be also presented (at the time of the full paper submission the tests will be performed), as well as analyzed, together with a roadmap definition for future developments.

1. INTRODUCTION

PERIGEO is an R&D project, funded by the INNPRONTA 2011-2014 programme from Spanish CDTI, and its goal is to create tools and methodologies that allow to continue the effort performed in laboratory (TRL 3-4) for space systems developments, exposing the technology to environmental and dynamic conditions that can be considered representative, to a certain extent, of the ones encountered in the target scene mission (TRL 5-6). For this purpose, PERIGEO aims to investigate the use of UAV technologies and processes for the validation of space oriented technologies.

Four different scenarios are considered in PERIGEO: Earth observation, interplanetary flight, atmospheric flight and *in-situ* exploration. According to the scenarios and the space missions defined for each one, the following challenges have been defined and are being afforded in PERIGEO:

- To define new **missions and vehicles design** by multidisciplinary optimization of its shape and configuration.
- To develop a **robust and fail tolerance control system**.
- To define new **autonomous navigation** methods based on optical sensors and its hybridization.
- To study an **integrated research and design process** that allows the use of real time data to increase the system performance.

As stated before, PERIGEO aims to increase the TRL level up to 5-6 by using UAV technologies for testing the systems developed. Several UAV flight campaigns have been defined to test technologies and scenarios under representative space conditions.

For this purpose, the main requirements at system and subsystem level have been extracted from the space missions and their restriction level and scalability evaluated. As an example, the LIDAR selection has been done based on its resolution, which is a key aspect on the technology and the scenario to be tested, and its cost. As a consequence, other requirements such as the range have been biased, but can be interpreted as a scale problem (increasing the range is feasible by increasing the cost, while the technology developed is not affected).

2. VISIONA: IMAGE AND LIDAR PROCESSING FOR SPACE ENVIRONMENTS

The VISIONA system has been designed in PERIGEO with the ultimate goal of providing inputs to a platform's Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) module and a Hazard Detection and Avoidance (HDA) module, acting as an intermediate piece of the whole mission chain. To do so, on one hand VISIONA is required to perform multi-modal navigation, that is, either in a relative or absolute mode. Coarsely, *relative* navigation refers to the propagation of the navigation states (that is, time-position-velocity-attitude, tPVA) expressed in a convenient reference frame e.g. global, local surface-attached, or local instrumental, between two epochs in which *absolute* navigation has been performed, that is, states have been estimated using external absolute information such as previously geo-referenced grounds landmarks when available. On the other hand, VISIONA uses LiDAR technology for environment perception by deriving elevation/terrain models, and aims to relate the LiDAR-derive information to the camera images, that is, to perform camera and LiDAR co-registration. The surface models and registered images are valuable inputs for HDA tasks.

Figure 1: VISIONA functional architecture

Figure 1 shows the high-level architecture designed for VISIONA, expressed as a sequential chain of algorithms acting on the sensor measurements (blue). In presence of a new camera image, VISIONA firstly pre-processes it to extract relevant features such as distinctive points and craters on the surface. In addition to the extraction, points are matched between consecutive images and craters are matched against a set of pre-extracted craters

from existing coordinated cartography of the surface. These two types of elements are the 'measurements' to perform state estimation, that is, navigation. Next, the update in navigation is used to derive a motion-corrected and re-gridded terrain model from the LiDAR measurements. From this digital model, again craters are extracted as distinctive features, and matched to those previously extracted from camera images. By doing so, the relative geometry between the terrain model and the camera image is estimated and, thus, camera and LiDAR images are co-registered (note that we will use the concept of 'LiDAR image' hereafter to refer to the 2.5D image constructed from the planimetric coordinates of the LiDAR ground points and the height component as 'pixel intensity').

3. CAPTURA AND INTEGRA: INS/GNSS (+imaging) PROCESSING

One of the Systems that provides INS/GNSS capability in PERIGEO is named CAPTURA (Figure 2). It consists of a HW that combines a commercial grade MEMS IMU sensor (EPSON M-G350PD11), a geodetic high-end GNSS receiver (Javad TRG3 OEM series) and the HW (based on a NetBurner PIC) that is in charge of capturing and saving the observations from both instruments. CAPTURA is also capable of communicating the data acquired from the navigation instruments via through a communication port. This is important in order to achieve real-time navigation capability to the combined system. Another important purpose of CAPTURA is to provide the time reference to all the observations generated in the system (inertial, optical and laser) in order to synchronize them to a common time reference.

Figure 2, CAPTURA PCB stack and external aspect

INS, GNSS observations (positions) and images generated estimations (positions and attitudes) can then be processed by INTEGRA in order to provide an accurate and precise estimation of navigation states.

INTEGRA is a navigation SW composed of a Stochastic Dynamic System (SDS) used for solving the differential equations that compose the INS and a hybridisation filter that is used to upgrade the estimated navigation states with the observation from the different instruments. In the case of INTEGRA, the user can select if he wants to use a Least Squares (LSQ) or a Iterative Extended Kalman Filter (IEKF) for the hybridisation calculus core or a RK4 or a variable step

Adams-Bashforth-Moulton algorithm for the numerical resolution of the navigation differential equations.

One of the great advantages of INTEGRA is its modularity. The navigation model equations can be adapted to the system according to the observations and the instruments the user has. These flexible modules are known as toolboxes. These toolboxes are implemented as a dynamic link library (DLL or SO files). In the case of PERIGEO, a classic loosely coupled approach INS/GNSS toolbox has been implemented and validated in the outdoor tests (known as PERIGEO-Air). Besides that, it is also planned that an INS/Imaging toolbox will be implemented for its validation in the simulation campaign that is parallel to the real tests that are planned in PERIGEO. This INS/imaging toolbox is an important piece of the combined system in order it is necessary to process the output data generated by VISIONA.

INTEGRA has been also implemented in such a generic way that may be compiled and used in different platforms as Windows and Linux. An off-line Windows version has been used and implemented for its utilization in the simulation campaign of PERIGEO project. As an example of the performance and flexibility of the SW, results from one of these simulations are shown in *Table 1*. This simulation assumed a deorbiting vehicle that was carrying out a reentry trajectory toward the Earth surface. It assumed that a tactical grade IMU and a geodetic level GNSS receiver were used as navigation instruments. Results show an acceptable performance for the reentry application.

Value	RMS	Unit
PosX:	0.051718	m
PosY:	0.041643	m
PosZ:	0.045858	m
VelX:	0.020164	m/s
VelY:	0.019625	m/s
VelZ:	0.022346	m/s
yaw:	0.016187	rad
pitch:	0.012233	rad
roll:	0.006105	rad

Table 1, Reentry trajectory simulation results obtained with INTEGRA

For real-time processing, a special version has been compiled in RTEMS32 and implemented in a LEON-3 based architecture computer known as Fault Tolerant Processing Architecture (FTP) in PERIGEO project. This FTP was the INS/GNSS processor of the system that has been used in the outdoor test.

Figure 3 shows the high-level architecture of the system that has been tested. The final implementation of such architecture is observed in *Figure 11*.

Figure 3, High level architecture of navigation system VISIONA/CAPTURA/INTEGRA(FTP) suite for PERIGEO.

It must be remarked that VISIONA output has not been implemented in the current version of real-time INTEGRA processor. But it is intended to be validated in the simulation campaign.

4. EARTH ANALOGUE CONDITIONS FOR TESTING ON UAVS PLATFORMS

Project testing is a key component in PERIGEO, as the project seeks to increase the TRL of the developed technologies using UAVs as a means for this purpose. Genuine space sensors and systems are not available within the project –thus, the scalability and restrictions of the previously discussed requirements have been analyzed and the appropriate technologies have been selected to be tested in-flight. As an example, the short LiDAR sensor scanning range is regarded as a ‘scale problem’, in which cost and performance are clearly correlated. In this case, modulating the mission flying altitude enables the use of LiDAR within the project. *Figure 4* shows the VISIONA system developed within PERIGEO, and sensors to be integrated (camera and LIDAR).

Figure 4: VISIONA system (left), camera and LIDAR sensors (right)

The algorithms have been extensively validated within simulation by using synthetic images of planetary terrains, as shown in *Figure 5* and *Figure 6*. This validation phase has been performed by using the ESD (Dual-Synthetic Environment) tool developed also in PERIGEO, which allows to test the algorithms while

prototyping in realistic conditions and faster than performing outdoor tests.

Figure 5: Example of features extraction and tracking results for two consecutive synthetic images

Figure 6: Example of 3D terrain reconstruction based on LIDAR data with motion correction and regridding (red lines represent the ground truth and green lines the reconstructed terrain)

One of the key challenges has been to extrapolate the tests performed in the ESD to real outdoor environments. As a previous step to the UAVs flights, several tests in outdoor environments have been also performed before the flights in order to adequate the sensors configuration (e.g. aperture, integration time, range, resolution, etc) and to anticipate particularities. As shown in Figure 7, a regular sandy terrain was observed, featuring two types of craters: three holes on the ground, of approximately 8, 5 and 7 centimeters of diameter, and 3 centimeters of depth, and four sand boulders, covered by brownish tissue, of around 10, 10, 8 and 10 centimeters of diameter and 5 centimeters of height, approximately. Example of preliminary results for this testing scenario are also shown.

Finally, the real testbed for the flight campaign was defined and adequated for the test. The flight area selected was located in Sevilla (coordinates $-5^{\circ}\text{E } 37^{\circ}\text{N}$ approximately), which is shown in Figure 8. In order to simulate a planetary surface, several artificial craters were installed and distributed among an area of 30x70 meters approximately. The final testbed configuration is shown in Figure 9. In order to generate differential corrections, a base GNSS L1/L2 station was installed and measurements of each crater center were performed, to be used for absolute navigation. For each crater campaign, the crater centers were measured due to their different locations.

Figure 7: Preliminary real test scenario (top) and an example of the features extraction and tracking results obtained (bottom)

Figure 8: Flight area selected to perform the tests with UAV, located in Sevilla.

Figure 9: Final configuration of the flight area with the artificial craters already deployed

5. UAV INTEGRATION

The algorithms developed within the PERIGEO project have been embedded into hardware platforms and the entire system has been integrated as payload into the UAV platform, together with the sensors and other hardware elements required (e.g. batteries, power distribution system, antennas, etc). For this purpose, a CAD model of each component was created and the allocation of the components was first studied, as illustrated in Figure 10. A carbon frame was also design and manufactured in order to attach the equipment to the UAV without modifying it.

Figure 10: Payload integration design and allocation based on CAD models of each component (including sensors)

The tests were performed using the SARAH helicopter from CATEC. SARAH is a rotatory-wing UAV with a payload capacity of 5-7 kg. It is fully electrical and have an autonomy of 30 minutes. It can be flown completely autonomously (autopilot and control station from Flying-Cam) including take-off and landing. In addition, to control the UAV, a WI-FI radiolink was installed in a control van. The Figure 11 shows the integration process with the hardware elements and the SARAH, while the Figure 12 shows the payload final integration into the UAV just before flying.

Figure 11: Payload integration (left) and installation into the UAV (right) before performing outdoor tests

Several flights plans have been also defined in order to simulate space missions challenges. In particular, four scenarios are being considered: terrain mapping, planetary landing, relative navigation and absolute navigation. Different altitudes and manoeuvres have been defined.

Figure 12: Payload final integration into the SARAH UAV (without the batteries endorsed)

Finally, the Figure 13 shows an example of the real flights performed with the SARAH and the systems developed already on board, capturing and processing data for which results are presented in next section. In total, more than 40 flights were performed.

Figure 13: Flight testing of the UAV SARAH with the payload already embedded and running

6. RESULTS

This section presents the results for the mapping scenario. The camera images were taken in three different heights allowing to test the robustness of the algorithms in terms of scale and rotation changes. For the LiDAR case, the different heights allow us to validate the DEM generation process, evaluate the DTM in terms of points/m², and evaluate the quality of the re-gridding. The combined camera and laser data allow us also the check the co-registration algorithms.

Figure 14: Flight profile for the mission analysed in terms of 3 spatial axis (top) and height (bottom)

In order to facilitate the processing and analysis of the obtained results, the flight was split in six parts according to different flight phases. Figure 14 shows the reference trajectory that comes from the UAV autopilot. This solution was estimated using inertial and magnetometer data together with GNSS in RTK mode. This flight corresponds to a mapping campaign in three different heights: 10 m (Orange), 15 m (green) and 20 m (cyan). The blue line corresponds to transition phase between heights. The take-off phase is shown in red while the landing phase is shown in black. The units are in meters.

Features and craters extraction and matching

The Figure 15 shows some extracted and matched points in a pair of overlapping images as well as an

example of matched points in two (green) and three images (blue), and points that are not matched (red). Note that due to low texture of terrain from test field, most of the matched points are clustered around the artificial craters.

Figure 15: Features extraction and tracking, where green points are matching in two consecutive images, blue points are matching in three consecutive images and red points are no matching.

Regarding the craters detection, the Figure 16 shows an example of results for different altitudes. From the results, it can be observed that the VISIONA system is able to robustly detect craters, with two different sizes, for 20 meters down to 10 meters of altitude.

Figure 16: Craters detection results

Figure 17 shows an example of crater matching between acquired image (left) and the craters database (right) for the 20 meters of altitude. Each crater matching pair is shown with a different color. From the results of this scenario, it can be observed that the crater matching process is non-dependant of the flying direction.

Figure 17: Results for the craters matching process

Optical Relative Navigation

The following figures shows the obtained results for N E and h position component, using the relative navigation mode with the coarse (blue) and fine option (green), compared to reference solution (red). The reference solution corresponds to the SARAH platform, estimated using INS/RTK GNSS. The results are

expressed in a local East North Up reference frame and the units are in meters.

Figure 18: Relative navigation results for the N and E component for the 20 meters altitude profile

From the relative navigation results, some interesting conclusions can be derived for the mapping scenario:

- The relative navigation results have a strong correlation with number of the matched points. Very few points for a certain epoch can lead to a bad estimation of the position and orientation for that epoch translating to a bad absolute position for the rest of processed epochs.
- The fine relative mode (green line) seems to be a little bit more robust in relation to the coarse mode.

Optical Absolute Navigation

The Figure 19 shows the absolute results for the mapping scenario at an altitude of 20 meters. Other altitudes and datasets are being processed at the time of writing this paper.

Figure 19: Absolute navigation results for the North and East components

The following preliminary conclusions can be extracted:

- The proposed crater distribution, with only two sizes craters, cause failures in crater matching process since it represents a high degree of homogeneity.
- The matching results have been improved by reducing the number of craters with absolute coordinates.
- Absolute navigation depends strongly with the number of detected craters. Less than 7/8 craters may lead to poor navigation results.

The proposed absolute navigation algorithm probes to be very good for estimating East and North components and also the heading component.

Digital Terrain Model generation

The Figure 20 shows the Fast DTM generated (15 m height) combining the reference trajectory together with raw laser measurements (green). After coarse DTM generation, dense DTM is computed (blue). Note that after interpolation we are able to reconstruct surface (especially craters) with very few laser lines. In order to generate a DTM, a trajectory is needed. To evaluate the process, the reference trajectory has been used as input trajectory for DTM. Note that a proper surface reconstruction depends highly with the quality of the input trajectory.

Figure 20: Results for Digital Terrain Model reconstruction from LIDAR data

7. CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in this paper represent the last phase of the PERIGEO project, where real test flight in UAVs for outdoor environments have been performed. Several conclusions can be addressed:

- The methodology proposed for scaling the space environments and systems to Earth environments and systems has been positively validated.
- The embedding and testing of the algorithms on UAVs in outdoor environments clearly represent an increment on the TRL level of the technology. Several problems and particularities have to be considered and addressed respect to the simulation scenario.
- Very promising results for optical absolute and relative navigation (using only images as sensor data) have been presented, as well as results for the digital terrain model reconstruction for LIDAR data.

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